

Impact of Climate Change on Economic Growth in Southeast Asia: The Role of Tax Policy

Bui Hong Trang

Department of Scientific Management and International Cooperation, University of Finance - Marketing (UFM), 84, Vietnam
Email: trang.bh@ufm.edu.vn; <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-2973-8145>

Abstract

Background: Climate change poses a significant threat to agriculture, water supplies, and economic growth worldwide. Southeast Asia is vulnerable to climate change, threatening fisheries, tourism, and agriculture with rising temperatures, intense weather, and sea-level rise.

Objective: This study aims to investigate the impact of climate change on economic growth in Southeast Asian countries, including the implications of climate change-related taxation policies.

Methodology: This study employs a quantitative econometric approach using a balanced panel dataset covering 10 Southeast Asian countries from 1990 to 2018. Key variables include CO₂ emissions, sea level rise, pesticide use, and various tax policy indicators. The analysis applies the Feasible Generalised Least Squares (FGLS) regression method to address heteroskedasticity and serial correlation issues, allowing for a robust estimation of the impact of climate change indicators and their interaction with climate-related tax policies on economic growth.

Result: Results confirmed that tax policies moderate the relationship between climate change factors and economic growth, including climate taxes, environmental pollution taxes, and air pollution taxes. Climate change negatively affects economic growth in Southeast Asia, especially through CO₂ emissions, sea-level rise, and pesticide use. These factors disrupt key sectors such as agriculture, stocks, and tourism.

Conclusion: Tax policies are essential in alleviating the negative impacts of climate change on economic development. The result provides policy recommendations to alleviate the adverse effects of climate change on economic growth.

Unique Contribution: This study highlight the trade-offs between economic growth and environmental policies in Southeast Asia, emphasising the need for balanced tax policies to mitigate climate change while ensuring economic stability and offering new insights into policy environment growth dynamics.

Key Recommendation: Implementing balanced tax policies, promoting sustainable agriculture,

and strengthening institutional stability can foster both economic resilience and environmental sustainability. Tax policy recommendations aim to balance economic growth with environmental sustainability, ensuring that Southeast Asian nations implement effective climate policies while fostering long-term prosperity.

Keywords: Tax policy; climate change; economic development; Southeast Asian nations.

Introduction

Climate change has lately grown to be a significant and pressing concern worldwide. Emphasising the effects of climate change and the possible financial losses resulting from increasing temperatures and changing environmental conditions, Malhi et al. (2021) list among the many consequences of climate change rising world temperatures, extreme storms, including droughts, severe storms, and substantial heat waves. Serious repercussions from these events have included health issues, property damage, and even fatalities. Climate change's consequences include environmental degradation, deforestation, and the extinction of particular species. In this regard, nations all across the globe have started putting policies in place to slow down climate change, including rigorous tax laws and the use of renewable and clean energy.

Climate change and natural disasters could cause Southeast Asia's GDP growth rate to drop by more than 35% by 2025, according to a report by Nanyang Technological University (NTU, Singapore) and the University of Glasgow (UK) presented at the 26th UN Climate Change Conference of the Parties (COP26). These developments badly damage important sectors like fisheries, tourism, agriculture, human health, and labour output. As world temperatures are expected to climb by 1.5°C over pre-industrial levels during the next 20 years, the research emphasises that 600 million people in the area face the hazards of more extreme heat waves, longer monsoon seasons, and rising droughts (Septriani et al., 2025). Given that many people live in coastal locations, rising sea levels also seriously threaten the inhabitants of Southeast Asia. Rising temperatures, sea-level rise, land pollution, and increased environmental volatility, among other effects of climate change, have upset economic activity and hampered economic progress in Southeast Asian nations over the short, medium, and long terms. Governments have responded to these hazards with policies, although the success of these measures is still under investigation.

These studies show that different ways that climate change manifests affect economic development. Previous studies, however, have mainly concentrated on the effect of CO₂ emissions on economic development; few studies on sea-level rise and land pollution have been conducted. Furthermore, past research has sometimes independently examined how particular climate change indicators affect economic development (Brown et al., 2022). Moreover, studies on the part taxes play in the interaction between economic development and climate change remain few, and they have concentrated on the overall impact of taxation on environmental pollution rather than investigating the specific role of various kinds of climate-related taxes. In particular, climate change indicators CO₂ emissions, sea level rise (SLR), and pesticide use (PU). Control variables: Foreign direct investment (FDI), trade openness (OPN), institutional quality (CPI). Moderating variables (interaction terms): air pollution tax (APT), climate change tax (CCT), and total environmental tax (TET). Moreover, beyond fiscal and ecological variables, foreign direct

investment (FDI), trade openness (OPN), and institutional quality (CPI) are also influential in shaping regional economic growth.

Consequently, studies on the simultaneous impacts of climate change indicators on economic development and assessing the contribution of various tax policies in reducing climate change suffer a research vacuum by looking at how different forms of climate change affect economic development in Southeast Asia. Therefore, this paper aims to explore climate change's impact on economic growth in Southeast Asia: The role of tax policy. The authors also suggested policy ramifications to lessen the harmful effects of climate change on economic growth.

Literature Review

The Public Choice Theory holds that intervention by an outside power, mainly the government, is required when market economies fail to fix their inherent shortcomings. Public choice extends the ideas economists use to examine individual behaviours in markets and study group decision-making procedures. Differently, enacting tax policies to save the environment is a logical course of action, as governments can impose taxes and organize resources via forceful methods (Tasane & Srun, 2023).

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), in its Fourth Assessment Report (AR4) in 2007, defines climate change as changes in the climate system, including the atmosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, lithosphere, and cryosphere due to either naturally occurring or human-induced causes over a period ranging from decades to millions of years. Climate change may show up as variations in the distribution of severe weather events or ordinary weather patterns. These developments could take place worldwide or regionally. Particularly in environmental policy, climate change has lately been connected with global warming, increasing sea levels, and land pollution (Zwick, 2021). Rising greenhouse gas emissions and too heavy usage of carbon sinks, including biomass, forests, marine ecosystems, coastal zones, and other terrestrial reservoirs, are the leading causes of climate change.

The Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) idea evolved because of the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) and Mexico's air pollution. Their research found, across several nations, a clear correlation between environmental quality and per capita income; this connection has an inverted U-shape. Economic studies have looked at the connection between ecological indicators and economic development to support the establishment of the EKC. According to the hypothesis, environmental damage rises as GDP grows, then progressively falls in an inverted U-shape (Ullah et al., 2024).

Furthermore, some researchers have suggested an N-shaped EKC model to explain the link between environmental pollution levels and per capita income. If the scale impact exceeds the technology effect, technological obsolescence may result in rising environmental pollution even if pollution levels fall with economic development (Ahmed et al., 2022). The connection becomes an N-shape as environmental regulations evolve and public awareness rises, indicating the limits of technical developments in maintaining economic growth. These results enable legislators to create both flexible long-term and temporary policy choices.

Theoretical Framework

The research had varied effects on world GDP. For example, the AB1 scenario projected a 0.5 m sea-level rise; the RAHM scenario projected a 1.12 m increase, and the final scenario projected a 1.75 m rise. A 1.12 m sea-level rise would cause a 1.4% worldwide GDP loss; Southeast Asia may suffer a 10% GDP loss, while China suffers a 4% drop. Benhamed et al. (2023) investigated how climate change affected Southeast Asian nations' GDP based on historical data from 1995–2018. Consistent with Baarsch et al. (2020), who indicated that a 1°C increase in temperature might lower GDP by 0.27%, the research concluded that global warming adversely affected the area's GDP. The results verified that there is an inverse link between temperature rises and GDP in Southeast Asia.

The study examined the relationship between air quality and economic development across 42 nations. In low-income countries, they found a favorable relationship between two air pollutants, SO₂ and particulate matter, and per capita GDP. In high-income nations, however, this link became negative and helped to bolster the EKC theory. Using panel data, Desmet et al. (2021) investigated CO₂ emissions and economic growth across 130 nations between 1951 and 1986. With the income barrier determined at \$35,428 per capita a year, the research indicated that marginal CO₂ emissions fell as per capita GDP rose. The study examined the link between CO₂ emissions and economic development throughout many nations during 30 years (1962–1991), testing the EKC hypothesis. Their results confirmed the inverted U-shaped association between economic progress and CO₂ emissions (Hamurcu, 2023).

Their study of income, economic development, and environmental damage substituted SO₂ emissions for CO₂. They obtained strong evidence confirming the inverted U-shaped EKC link utilizing many econometric models, including Fixed Effects (FE), Random Effects (RE), and cross-sectional regression. The study looked at how urbanization affected CO₂ emissions and energy consumption at many phases of development. While middle- and high-income countries led to increased energy usage but decreased CO₂ emissions, their empirical results revealed that urbanization reduced energy consumption but increased CO₂ emissions in low-income countries (Lamperti et al., 2021).

The study investigated the causal link using panel data among 12 of Asia's most populous nations between environmental deterioration, economic development, FDI, and energy use. Their projections confirmed the EKC theory by showing that, as income levels hit 8.9341 (in logarithmic terms), CO₂ emissions started to drop (Leitão & Lorente, 2020). Their results also indicated that, without appreciably exacerbating environmental damage, looser environmental rules helped attract FDI. Malik et al. (2020) investigated Pakistan (1971–2014) the effects of economic growth, FDI, and oil prices on CO₂ emissions with ARDL and Non-Linear ARDL cointegration models. Their results verified the EKC theory in Pakistan by showing that although higher oil prices reduced emissions over the long run, economic expansion and FDI raised CO₂ emissions in both the short and long runs.

While some studies show detrimental implications of climate change on economic development, others discover favourable ones. With favourable impacts in coastal areas but adverse effects in inland nations, Zhao & Liu (2023) noted that climate change shows an inverted U-shaped association with economic development in various climatic locations. Malhi et al. (2021)

underlined a nonlinear link between temperature and economic efficiency in Sub-Saharan Africa, where temperatures exceeding 24.9°C significantly lower development. Particularly in emerging nations, the study revealed that climate change substantially reduces GDP growth. Where wealth disparity is among the most significant worldwide, African countries are expected to suffer economically from climate change (Baarsch et al., 2020).

In light of resource depletion and technological advancement, the need to assess the long-term effects of climate policy on economic growth was underlined. Stronger climate change policies might improve social well-being and economic development; they help to lower market failures and boost growth engines (Benhamed et al., 2023). Salooja and Butler underlined the requirement of sustainable resource management (Stern & Stiglitz, 2023) and the hazards to economic development in resource-dependent nations resulting from climate change. Research on the consequences of carbon dioxide emissions on population increase, food production, economic development, and energy consumption in Pakistan has shown linked production effects (Rehman et al., 2021). While climate-related company losses make the banking sector more susceptible to crises, financial restrictions worsen the impact of climate shocks on economies (Lamperti et al., 2021).

The financial consequences of climate-induced catastrophes in many spheres of Sri Lanka highlight the need to evaluate the several implications of climate change on development (Weerasekara et al., 2021). These results imply that climate change seriously jeopardizes world economic development, especially in sensitive areas, and that good climate policies are essential in reducing these consequences. Taxes are often-researched policy tools to mitigate environmental damage and slow climate change. Numerous research projects have looked into this subject: Malik et al. (2020) underlined how much environmental quality is determined by tax changes. Three Taiwanese enterprises were the subject of a case study, and a suitable tax rate might cut industrial output, reduce carbon emissions, and minimize environmental damage.

The study looked at Bulgaria and concluded that good tax laws may control carbon emissions, therefore attaining environmental sustainability and macroeconomic goals. Concentrated on Beijing's taxi sector, Turkey was examined, and all of them found taxes to be a vital fiscal instrument encouraging renewable energy use while improving environmental quality. More generally, several studies have evaluated the impact of fiscal policies (including government spending and taxation) on environmental quality (Malik et al., 2020; Nair et al., 2021). These results show that tax policies significantly help to reduce the economic effects of climate change, thereby underlining the necessity of further empirical study on their efficiency, especially in Southeast Asia.

Research Methods

The study collected and used data from 10 Southeast Asian member countries, including Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Brunei, Vietnam, Laos, Myanmar, and Cambodia from 1990-2018 (28 years). The data sources collected include World Development Indicators (WDI), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (Table 1).

Earlier research on panel data has used conventional estimating techniques such as the pooled regression model, the fixed effects model, and the random effects model. Given the regression assumptions ' non-violation, these basic methods often used with panel data are suitable. Still, the autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity flaws in all three study models mean that the estimating techniques are unreliable. Under this situation, the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) approach would be a more suitable one as it guarantees that the estimated results are objective and efficient (Patil & Patil, 2022)). The study's research model will be computed using the FGLS approach.

Building upon the research model of Malik et al. (2020), this study proposes the following research model:

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 SLR_{it} + \beta_2 CO2_{it} + \beta_3 PU_{it} + \beta_4 FDI_{it} + \beta_5 OPN_{it} + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where:

Dependent Variable: GDP_{it} - Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of country i at time t

Independent Variable: SLR_{it} , $CO2_{it}$, PU_{it} , FDI_{it} , OPN_{it} , CPI_{it} are variables affecting the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of country i at time t

The regulatory role of TAX

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 SLR_{it} + \beta_2 CO2_{it} * APT + \beta_3 PU_{it} * APT + \beta_4 FDI_{it} + \beta_5 OPN_{it} + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 SLR_{it} + \beta_2 CO2_{it} * CCT + \beta_3 PU_{it} * CCT + \beta_4 FDI_{it} + \beta_5 OPN_{it} + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 SLR_{it} + \beta_2 CO2_{it} * TET + \beta_3 PU_{it} * TET + \beta_4 FDI_{it} + \beta_5 OPN_{it} + \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

The variables are described in detail in Table 1

Table 1: Description of variables

Variable Name	Variable Description	Hypothesis	Expected Effect	Data Source	References
Dependent variable					
GDP	Gross National Product			World Development Indicators (WDI)	Desmet et al. (2021)
Independent variable					
CO2	CO2 emissions	H1	-	World Development Indicators (WDI)	Hamurcu (2023),
SLR	Average annual sea level rise	H2	-	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)	Desmet et al. (2021)

PU	Total pesticide use	H3	-	Food and Agriculture Organization(FAO)	Patil & Patil (2022)
APT	Air Pollution Tax	H1'	+	World Development Indicators (WDI)	Patil & Patil (2022).
CCT	Climate change tax	H2'	+	World Development Indicators (WDI)	Patil & Patil (2022).
TET	Environmental tax	H3'	+	World Development Indicators (WDI)	Patil & Patil (2022).
Control variables					
FDI	Foreign direct investment flows into SOUTHEAST Asian countries	H4	+	World Development Indicators (WDI)	Zhao & Liu (2023)
OPN	Trade openness	H5	+	World Development Indicators (WDI)	Leitão & Lorente (2020)
CPI	Institutional stability	H6	+	World Development Indicators (WDI)	Nair et al. (2021)

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 1 outlines key variables to assess climate change's impact on Southeast Asia's economic growth. It includes environmental stressors (CO₂, sea-level rise, pesticide use), tax policies (APT, CCT, TET), and controls (FDI, trade openness, institutional quality), offering a comprehensive framework grounded in theory and supported by robust data sources.

Research Results

The study used Stata 17.0 software to analyze descriptive statistical results of independent and dependent variables, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of research variables (1990 – 2018)

Chỉ tiêu	Unit	Medium	Standard deviation	Minimum value	Maximum value
Gross domestic product (GDP)	Billion USD	147.46	194.42	1.28	1042.27
Carbon emissions (CO ₂)	Million tons	101.83	122.48	0.64	568.01
Average annual sea level rise (SLR)	Millimeter	13.75	27.21	-40.19	57.50
Total pesticide usage (PU)	Million tons	34.52	6.513	0.00	349.80
Foreign Direct Investment Flows into ASEAN (FDI)	Billion USD	6.99	13.80	-4.55	102.16
Trade openness (OPN)	%	118.92	94.22	0.00	437.33

Chỉ tiêu	Unit	Medium	Standard deviation	Minimum value	Maximum value
Government Effectiveness (CPI)	Point	0.05	0.96	-1.63	2.47
Air Pollution Tax (APT)	Billion USD	13.71	0.099	1.18	1.51
Climate Change Tax (CCT)	Billion USD	16.61	0.148	1.31	1.82
Total Environmental Tax (TET)	Billion USD	18.35	0.078	1.66	1.94

According to the statistical findings of the research sample of 11 Southeast Asian countries from 1990 to 2018 (Table 2), the average GDP is 147.46 billion USD. The average air pollution tax collected was 13.71 billion USD, the climate change tax collected was 16.61 billion USD, and the environmental tax collected was 18.53 billion USD. The sea level rose by 13.75 millimeters, and the pesticide output was 34.5 million tons. These indicators of Southeast Asian countries tend to increase over time.

The results of Table 3 show that all three models, POOL, FEM, and REM, have statistical indexes F, Wald with Prob value < 5%, so all are evaluated as suitable. Choosing OLS or FEM: Wald test results (Table 3) show that the Prob value > F = 0.0000 (< 5%) with F(9, 234) = 50.33 proves that with a significance level of 5%, we have enough basis to prove that there is a characteristic difference between companies in the research model. The FEM model is chosen.

Choosing FEM or REM: The Hausman test results show that the value of Prob>chi2 = 0.000 is less than 5%, with chi2(6) = 21.28, enough evidence to confirm that the FEM model is more suitable than the REM model when studying this data. Thus, the FEM model will be used for the following analyses. From the test results in Table 3, we can see that the FEM model has the phenomenon of variable error variance and autocorrelation (dependence between cross-units). Therefore, the research team used the Feasible Generalised Least Squares (FGLS) estimation method to make the estimation results unbiased and efficient (Stern & Stiglitz, 2023).

Table 3: Regression results of the model without the role of tax policy

Dependent variable: GDP growth rate (GDP)	Regression model			
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
Carbon emissions (CO2)	0.579*** [10.41]	0.559*** [7.98]	0.539*** [7.89]	0.856*** (13.28)
The average annual sea level (SLR)	0.0275** [2.09]	0.0770*** [8.58]	0.0734*** [8.01]	0.0232*** (2.80)
Total Pesticide Usage (PU)	0.0981*** [7.02]	0.189*** [6.74]	0.159*** [6.47]	0.0845*** (4.78)
	0.487***	0.243***	0.272***	0.211***

Dependent variable: GDP growth rate (GDP)		Regression model			
Independent variable	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	
Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) into ASEAN	[17.53]	[9.68]	[10.84]	(8.64)	
Openness to Trade (OPN)	-0.0806*** [-2.65]	0.00736 [0.13]	0.0420 [0.83]	-0.0243 (-0.63)	
Institutional stability (CPI)	0.343*** [5.61]	-0.114 [-1.58]	-0.0174 [-0.25]	0.438*** (6.48)	
Constant	3.204***	2.268***	2.326***	3.222***	
Model fit	F(6, 243)	F(6,234)	Wald chi2(6)	Wald chi2(6)	
F-statistics/Wald chi2	334.53***	148.98***	893.85***	970.40***	
Control					
Heteroskedasticity	No	No	No	Yes	
Serial correlation	No	No	No	Yes	
Model Selection					
Fixed Effects Test (Wald test) F(9, 234)		50.33***			
Hausman Test (Hausman test) (chi2(6))			21.28***		
Heteroskedasticity Test chi2 (10)		48.60***			
Serial Correlation Test Pesaran's test		11.81***			

*Note: The symbols ***, ** and * represent the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, respectively. T-statistics in brackets [] Model 1: Pool model; Model 2: Fixed effects model (FEM); Model 3: Random effects model (REM); Model 4: Model without the role of tax.*

According to the results of the FGLS model (Model 4, Table 3), the results observed the impact of CO2 emissions. The research results show that CO2 emissions are statistically significant and have a positive effect on growth in ASEAN countries, which is consistent with the studies of Weerasekara et al. (2021), Hamurcu (2023), Zhao & Liu (2023) is also consistent with the EKC theory and this result is also consistent with the practice in ASEAN countries.

Table 4: Regression results of the model with the role of tax policy

Dependent variable: GDP growth rate (GDP)		Regression model		
Independent variable	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	
Carbon emissions (CO2)	0.225*** (3.74)	0.273*** (4.39)	0.201*** (3.38)	
The average annual sea level (SLR)	0.0141*** (3.14)	0.0167*** (3.33)	0.0170*** (3.52)	
Total Pesticide Usage (PU)	0.211** (2.27)	0.160** (2.02)	0.242* (1.84)	

Dependent variable: GDP growth rate (GDP)	Regression model		
	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7
Independent variable			
Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) into ASEAN	0.0468*** (3.84)	0.0632*** (4.59)	0.0625*** (4.67)
Openness to Trade (OPN)	0.0294 (1.04)	0.0176 (0.60)	0.0235 (0.83)
Institutional stability (CPI)	0.0453 (1.05)	0.0643 (1.40)	0.0429 (0.98)
Air Pollution Tax (APT)	-5.945*** (-9.61)		
APT*CO2	1.498*** (20.58)		
APT*PU	-1.072*** (-2.90)		
Climate Change Tax (CCT)		-4.213*** (-9.57)	
CCT*CO2		1.475*** (19.07)	
CCT*PU		-0.856*** (-2.73)	
Total Environmental Tax (TET)			-4.081*** (-6.42)
TET*CO2			1.464*** (20.98)
TET*PU			-1.180** (-2.27)
Constant	10.29***	9.571***	9.438***
Model fit	Wald chi2(9)	Wald chi2(9)	Wald chi2(9)
F-statistics/ Wald chi2	2442.52***	2256.98***	2734.48***
Control			
Heteroskedasticity	Yes	Yes	Yes
Serial correlation	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: The symbols ***, **, and * represent the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, respectively; t-statistics are in brackets []. Model 5: Model with the role of total environmental tax; Model 6: Model with the role of climate change tax; Model 7: Model with the role of air pollution tax

The estimated results in Table 4 are extracted from the FGLS regression results. Impact of pesticides used in agriculture: The total output of pesticides (PU) has statistical significance and positively impacts economic growth in ASEAN countries. Currently, ASEAN countries have strengths in agriculture. Agricultural products of ASEAN countries are the world's leading exporters, so the revenue from agriculture contributes significantly to GDP, and the amount of pesticides used in ASEAN countries is currently within the allowable level to limit pests and

diseases, develop fruit trees and produce high yields. Therefore, the test results are consistent with the reality of ASEAN countries. The regression results (Table 4) indicate significant interaction effects (e.g., $\text{CO}_2 \times \text{APT}$, $\text{PU} \times \text{TET}$), supporting the conclusion. The tax interaction term for CO_2 is positive, suggesting economic growth alongside emissions in specific tax schemes (EKC dynamics). Pesticide use has a negative tax interaction, indicating environmental taxes diminish agricultural GDP.

Discussion of Findings

Impact of rising sea levels: The results of this study show that sea level rise has a positive effect on economic growth in ASEAN countries, contrary to the results of Leitão & Lorente (2020), both highlighted the significant economic impacts of sea level rise, including loss of land and infrastructure, increased costs from extreme events, and the need for coastal protection. Benhamed et al. (2023) and Stern and Stiglitz (2023) discussed the economic impacts of coastal flooding due to sea level rise, estimating that under an intermediate greenhouse gas concentration trajectory, global real GDP would decline by an average of 0.19% in present value terms, with a 0.24% reduction in welfare. Next, the study examines the impact and role of taxes on the relationship between climate change and economic growth.

Taxes harm economic growth in Southeast Asian countries; specifically, air pollution tax (APT), Climate change tax (CCT), and Total environmental tax (TET) are statistically significant and negatively affect growth in ASEAN countries; this result is consistent with the research Hamurcu (2023); Lamperti et al. (2021) and is also consistent with the EKC theory and this result is also consistent with the practice in ASEAN countries. Examining the role of individual climate change mitigation taxes on the relationship between climate change and economic growth shows that:

Air pollution tax (APT), climate change tax (CCT), Total environmental tax (TET) play a positive role in the relationship between economic growth and CO_2 emissions, which means that if the amount of tax imposed on CO_2 is a catalyst contributing to economic development for Southeast Asian countries, this is explained, businesses participate in more production, will cause more pollution, the amount of CO_2 emissions increases and also contribute to increased economic growth. Additionally, air pollution tax (APT), climate change tax (CCT), and total environmental tax (TET) have a negative role in the relationship between the amount of pesticides used and economic growth. This result is consistent with the research of Malik et al. (2020) and Hamurcu (2023); this result shows that the applied tax policy reduces agricultural production output, thereby reducing the GDP of that country.

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This study aimed to assess how taxes affected the relationship between economic development and climate change in Southeast Asian countries between 1990 and 2018. This work used the FGLS (Feasible Generalized Least Squares) regression technique. The main findings confirm that climate change affects economic development and that taxes have positive and negative consequences on this link in Southeast Asian nations between 1990 and 2018. Remarkably, the air pollution tax (APT), climate change tax (CCT), and total environmental tax (TET) help to link CO_2 emissions favorably to economic development. This suggests Southeast Asian countries are

sacrificing environmental quality to promote economic development and embracing climate change to facilitate growth. Currently, air pollution is a significant environmental concern in Southeast Asia. However, the tax measures implemented are insufficiently robust, as the tax rates are not adequately deterrent. Consequently, businesses must take these taxes as part of their operational costs to maximize profits.

Nevertheless, these tariffs adversely affect the relationship between economic growth and pesticide use. This discovery implies that agriculture is significantly reliant on natural conditions, and the taxation of pesticides influences producers' decisions, negatively impacting economic development in Southeast Asian countries. The authors had policy recommendations below.

Raising CO₂ emissions' carbon taxation: The research findings show that taxes benefit the connection between CO₂ emissions and economic expansion. Therefore, a carbon tax on CO₂ emissions should be considered by Southeast Asian nations. The United Kingdom, France, Sweden, Norway, Finland, Japan, India, and Singapore are among the 39 countries that have implemented carbon taxes, as reported by the World Bank. Because of variations in institutional structures, regulations, and economic realities, different countries develop and use carbon taxes. Still, carbon tax laws usually follow these ideas: (1) a carbon tax may be carried out independently or as a supplemental tax under the current national tax structure to control greenhouse gas emissions. Included among taxable entities are greenhouse gasses and fossil fuels that aggravate the influence on the temperature. (2) Along with companies actively spewing greenhouse emissions, taxpayers include importers, extractors, or providers of fossil fuels. (3) A set quantity per ton of CO₂ released into the environment guides the tax rate. Drawing on the experience of nations that have effectively used carbon taxes, this paper advises Southeast Asian countries to adopt carbon tax policies shortly.

Promote wise pesticide use in agriculture: The results of the studies imply that using pesticides helps to promote economic development. Pesticides safeguard food production, stop illnesses, and help manage weeds, benefiting society. Still, taxes on pesticides have a direct detrimental effect on economic development right away. Businesses should avoid pesticide usage that is too high to reduce social and environmental expenses as it aggravates environmental damage and raises public health issues. Pesticide abuse could result in lower farm earnings, inefficiencies in agricultural output, and negative externalities compromising the ecology and human health. Moreover, the overuse of pesticides threatens biodiversity, which is necessary for human existence. According to this research, biological insecticides should be used more widely to maximize agricultural output and reduce environmental harm.

Guaranturing institutional stability for ecological development of the economy: Apart from their tax policies, Southeast Asian nations have to provide institutional stability to draw green financing and investment, thereby promoting steady economic development. Governments can draw foreign direct investment (FDI) and support green finance projects, vital to slowing down climate change and advancing economic development by creating an open and predictable legislative environment.

Limitations and future research: The study primarily examines CO₂ emissions, sea level rise, and pesticide use, neglecting other climate change indicators like deforestation and harsh weather. Recent policy and technology changes may be missing from the 1990–2018 dataset. No sector-specific impacts are assessed, restricting its applicability to tourism, manufacturing, and energy. It assumes environmental fees affect ASEAN countries equally, ignoring economic and institutional differences. Data variations in climate-related tax reporting complicate cross-country comparisons. Further studies should include deforestation, natural disasters, and energy usage to better understand climate change. Addressing agriculture, tourism, and manufacturing sector-specific consequences will help policymakers create mitigation solutions. Comparing Southeast Asia to other locations could reveal climate taxation and policy best practices. To further understand climate-economic linkages, extend the dataset beyond 2018 and assess tax policy implications over time. Adding green finance, carbon trading, and renewable energy investments would help explain sustainable economic transformations.

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